

Examining the Impact of Career Coaching Practices on Career Decision Self-Efficacy and Career Stress Levels of University Students: The Case of Izmir Katip Çelebi University

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Abstract

The choices made by university students in the process of making career decisions are one of the most important decisions they make in their lives. The aim of this study is to examine the impact of career coaching practices on the career decision self-efficacy and career stress levels of university students. The sample of the study is of senior students studying in the Department of Business Administration of Izmir Katip Çelebi University in the 2018-2019 academic year. A total of 24 people were taken to the study, including 12 (6 females and 6 males) in the study group and 12 (6 females and 6 males) in the control group. Sociodemographic form, Career Decision Self-Efficacy Scale (CDSSES) and Career Stress Scale (CSC) were used as data collection tools. The students in the experimental group were given a 6-week career coaching program developed by the researcher, each for 60 minutes. Levene's test, t-test and ancova were used in statistical data analysis. As a result of the study, it was determined that the practice of career coaching increases the career decision self-efficacy of the students in the working group and reduces their level of career stress.

Keywords: Career, Coaching, Stress management, Career Stress, Career Coaching

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1. Introduction

A career is the progress of individuals in the profession of their choice and developing their skills by gaining experience during the process they are in that profession (Bayraktaroglu, 2003). Although the first emergence of the concept of career was known as from the 16th century onwards, its scientific use for business and humanity was in Anne Roe's 1956 book "Psychology of Angels". In 1956,

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Donald E. Supper's "Career Psychology" was Triedemen and Ohara's "Theory of Career Development, Choice and Adaptation and Individual Career Development Theory", as well as John Holland's "Career Preference Theory" in 1966, came front in career topics and brought this concept into the discussion (Cetin, 2008).

Today, the traditional career approach, which is increasingly losing its influence, has been replaced by a dynamic, new and boundaryless career approach (Simsek, 2004). When the literature in the field of professional guidance and career counselling is examined, it is seen that approaches and theories explaining the career development process and career selection are divided into different categories. When looking at the types of career theories, it is known that the basic approach of Trait-Factor Theories is based on the idea that harmonization of the characteristics of the individual and the professional environment will provide professional success and job satisfaction. The first feature-factor-compliant theories are Parsons's *Trait-Factor Theory*, which are then the *Minnesota Theory of Work Adjustment (MTWA)* and *Holland's Typology Theory* respectively (Kuzgun, 2019). Life-Span Theories focus on different life stages and explain career behaviours specific to these stages. Although there are many life-period theories, the most widely used and accepted theories are Gottfredson's "*Circumscription, Compromise and Self-Concept*" theory and Donald Super's "*Career Development Stages*" theory (Unsal, 2014). Learning Theories focus on a wide group of variables that influence the lifelong career process and career choices, arguing that social conditions, social status, and life events have a meaningful impact on career choices. Learning theories: Krumboltz's "*Social Learning and Planned Happenstance Theory*" and Lent, Brown, and Hackett's "*Social Cognitive Career Theory*" (Yeşilparmak, 2018). Social Cognitive Career Theory focuses on individuals' belief that they can do something successfully. It is seen that this belief within the individual plays a fundamental role in their career choice and decision interests, values and abilities (Sharf, 2017). On the other hand, research has determined that some people make their career decisions easily without any difficulties, and others have problems through very difficult processes during the decision phase (Öztemel, 2012). In the studies, it was looked at which factors may affect career indecisiveness and it was seen that it is divided into two parts. While some research focuses on the relationship between career indecisiveness and professional maturity, confidence, self-esteem, unwise beliefs (Hamamcı and Çoban, 2007; Santos, 2001) and several other studies focused on career indecisiveness and self-esteem and control (Gati et al., 2012; Lee, Yu & Lee, 2008). It can be seen as a reason to feel competent to make or not to make career decisions (Creed, Patton & Prideaux, 2006). When the literature was examined, it was determined that the perception of self-efficacy affected the professional preferences and career plans of individuals, especially university students (Hackett & Betz, 1989; Öztemel, 2012). Students with a high level of career decision-making self-efficacy were also found to experience lower levels of career indecisiveness (Creed, Patton & Prideaux, 2006; Gati, et al., 2012). Similarly, a three-year follow-up study by Guay, Ratelle, Sénécal, Larose and Deschênes (2006) found that individuals with high levels of self-esteem had low levels of career indecisiveness.

Individuals may face various difficulties in the career decision-making and planning process, as well as various role conflicts in their professional life, communication problems, role uncertainty, excessive workload, leadership problems, etc. are affected by various stress factors (Saka and Gati, 2007). Career stress occurs at different stages of a people's career journey and in various ways. The expectations and thoughts of the students at the university about their careers cause stress (Özden & Berk, 2011). In many studies, especially involving students studying at the university, it has been observed that students are much more stressed than other people (Donat et al., 2019). It has been observed that most students have difficulty making an effective career plan and these students experience psychological disorders such as anxiety and depression, and therefore their stress level is high. It was determined that students who took the necessary steps in career planning and made a suitable career decision had fewer depressive moods and lower stress levels compared to those who were indecisive (Erkan et al., 2012).

Coaching is a process that helps other individuals develop, learn things, and take their performance to the next level (Payne, 2007). If we look at the history of coaching in the field of education; it was first used in 1840 to indicate the special instructors who prepared students for the exam at Oxford University (Çetin, 2008). Although the spread of coaching as a profession date back to the 1980s, its service as a profession in Turkey began with the publication of the Official Gazette dated June 29, 2013, numbered 28692 (www.resmigazete.gov.tr). Coaching is not a therapy, counselling, or mentoring. Career coaching helps people raise awareness of their self-efficacy levels, encourage them to act, and creates the roadmap they need to achieve their goals (Voss, 2002). The place of coaching, which has gained increasing importance in our country in recent years and is considered a profession especially after it is published in the official newspaper, has just started to develop. Career goals and objectives, which were initially studied under the name of life coaching and student coaching, have now become a separate issue. Because it has been observed that the choices made by university students, especially in the process of making career decisions occupy an important part of their lives. Students need to get to know themselves well, discover their own abilities and set their goals correctly when making a decision that is so important to their lives. In this respect, making the right career decisions is a very difficult and important process (Işık, 2014). Especially students who are in the transition period from school life to work-life need to make career decisions, try to make career plans, evaluate their career options, apply for jobs, and do some research to test the suitability of positions for them. To fully maintain the physiological and psychological structures of the senior students, the need for psychological support is visible in their applications such as accurately evaluating their career goals and potentials, collecting information about these subjects, conducting research, evaluating themselves correctly, and implementing their plans (Cetin, 2008). When the studies on the careers of university students were examined in our country, it was determined that there were quite a few studies. Career centres established in universities can be seen as the beginning of these studies. The first examples of career centres established in Turkey for career interventions are applications at Middle East Technical

University and Bilkent University (Zeren et al., 2017). In a 2013 study conducted by Yoğun, career centres in our country were evaluated and it was informed that only 24 of the career centres in 110 universities were actively working (Yoğun, 2013). In other words, it is seen that not all career centres established in universities are up-to-date, activities differ by institution, there are uncertainties in their functions and common results such as the insufficient number of career centres are achieved (Zeren et al., 2017). In 2018, the presidency announced that all these problems should be addressed by establishing operational career centres at every university, and three new services for career centres were raised from the Presidential Office of Human Resources. Within the scope of this service, common information on "University Career Centres Book", "Talent Gate" and "Career Planning Course Sample Curriculum" was provided to the universities and support was provided. Thus, it is aimed to create co-managed centres (www.cbiko.gov.tr).

Coaching programs are needed to be developed to determine university students' careers more realistically and to keep their stress levels under control given the difficulties that they have in achieving their goals and not knowing themselves adequately. Together with coaching programs and practices, university students will be allowed to manage this process in a more positive way by choosing a career that is in line with their expectations and goals. From this point on, the aim of this research is to examine the impact of career coaching practices on the career decision self-efficacy and career stress levels of university students. For this purpose, the hypotheses to be tested in our research are:

H₁: The average scores of the students in the experimental group who are intervened by applying career coaching from the Career Decision Self-Efficacy Expectancy scale are higher than the scores of the students in the control group who are not applied to career coaching from the career decision self-efficacy scale.

H₂: The career stress levels of the students in the experimental group who are intervened by applying career coaching are lower than the career stress levels of the students in the control group who are not exposed to career coaching.

2. Methodology

This study is a semi-experimental study examining the impact of career coaching practices on career decision self-efficacy and career stress levels of university students. In our study, a mixed pattern with a control group was used using pre-test and post-test. In the study, the independent variable is coaching practices and dependent variables are determined as career decision self-efficacy and career stress. In our study, measurements made at different times were applied to both the experimental and control groups.

2.1. Sample

The population of the study is made up of students studying at Izmir Katip Çelebi University Department of Business Administration in the 2018-2019 academic year. The sample of the study is of senior students studying in the Department of Business Administration of Izmir Katip Çelebi University in the 2018-2019 academic year. The reason for choosing university senior students is that individuals in the transition stage to professional life undergo a relatively more intensive decision and intellectual process than other class students in the process of evaluating the appropriate career options for them. For this reason, it is considered important to reveal the variables that affect the levels of self-efficacy in making career decisions. (Super et al., 1957). In the study, the convenience sample, one of the non-probability sampling methods, was selected as the sampling method. Convenience sampling is a non-random type of sampling in which any segment of the sample to be selected from the population is determined by the researcher and taken into 50 studies. In the convenience sampling method, also called random sampling, data are collected from the population in the fastest, easiest and most economical way (Haşiloğlu et al., 2015). It was determined that the convenience sampling method was preferred in 90% of the research conducted in our country (Kurtuluş, 2004). In this study, the reasons for choosing the convenience sampling method are the accessibility of the sample and the time constraint. In this study, which was carried out by using the convenience sampling method, senior students were informed about the research and the career decision self-efficacy scale and career stress scale were applied. After the application of the scales, a preliminary interview was made with the students and general information was given about the details, content, duration of the research, and the importance of attending the sessions, and experimental and control groups were formed among the students on a voluntary basis. 1 student who did not want to participate in the study was excluded from the research. A total of 24 people, 12 (6 females and 6 males) for the experimental group and 12 (7 females and 5 males) for the control group, were included in the study. Since the participation in the study was based entirely on volunteerism, oral consent was obtained from the researchers during the preliminary interview. The students in the two groups were matched in terms of age, success levels and experiences and homogeneous groups were formed within themselves. In the preliminary interview, it was objectively proved that the two groups were like each other. Even if the data collected can be out of date, when the literature is examined, the subject focused on the study maintains its originality.

2.2. Data Collection Tools

Socio-demographic Form: It is a form prepared by the researcher in the form of a questionnaire to obtain the socio-demographic information of the students who will participate in the study.

Career Decision Self-Efficacy Scale (CDSE): Developed by Taylor and Betz (1983), the scale consisting of 25 questions aims to measure the levels of decision-making self-efficacy of university students regarding career decisions. The

items of the scale are 'I don't trust at all', 'I don't trust', 'I trust very little', 'I trust', 'I trust a lot'. Validity and reliability studies of the scale were carried out by Ulaş and Yildirim (2016). As a result of the explanatory and validating factor analyses, it was found that the scale was 5 factors; two semi-test reliability were also examined and identified as Cronbach Alpha= .95. The 5-factor sub-dimensions of the scale are as follows: a) Accurate self-assessment, b) Gathering information about professions, c) Setting goals, d) Planning for the future, e) problem-solving behaviours.

Korean Career Stress Inventory (KCSI): Created by Choi and her colleagues (2011) to measure the level of stress associated with the careers of university students. Validity and reliability studies of the scale were carried out by Özden and Berk (2017). The scale consists of a total of 20 items and 4 subdivisions: "career uncertainty", "lack of knowledge", "employment pressure" and "external conflict". The items of the scale are of type 5 Likert, ranging from "I do *not agree at all* (1)" to "I *completely agree* (5)".

2.3. Career Coaching Practices

In this study, a total of 6 sessions of career coaching were performed each session lasting for 60 minutes on 12 students who formed the experimental group and were selected on a voluntary basis. The sessions were held once in a week. The sessions were held by the researcher at Izmir Katip Çelebi University Institute of Social Sciences. The contents of the sessions were prepared by the researcher based on Social Cognitive Career Theory. The sessions of the coaching practices applied to the experimental group, which lasted 6 sessions, were planned as follows: *1st Session: Introduction and Introduction, 2nd Session: Self-Assessment Studies, 3rd Session: Collecting Information about Professions, 4th Session: Setting Goals and Planning, 5th Session: Solving Problems, making a CV and Job Interview Preparation, 6th Session: Conclusion and Evaluation.*

2.4. Process

In this study, which was held using the easy sampling method, senior students were informed about the research and Career Decision Self-Efficacy Scale (CDSE) and Korean Career Stress Inventory (KCSI) were applied. After the implementation of the scales, the students were given general information by pre-interviewing about the details, content, duration, and importance of attending the sessions, and experimental and control groups were formed among the students on a voluntary basis. One student who did not want to participate in the study was excluded from the study. A total of 24 people were taken to the study, including 12 (6 females and 6 males) for the experimental group and 12 (7 females and 5 males) for the control group. Since participation in the study was created entirely on a voluntary basis, oral consent was obtained from the researchers during the preliminary interview.

A 6-week career coaching program developed by the researcher was applied to the students in the experimental group between May 14 and June 18, 2019, each for 60 minutes. No application was made to the students in the control group. While preparing career coaching practices for university students, previous studies based on social cognitive career theory were examined (Işık, 2010) and because of literature reviews, a program of 6 sessions was created by obtaining information from experts on the subject. The 6-session module, which was prepared and like other studies in terms of content, was applied to each student for 6 hours. Throughout the research, a total of 72 hours of coaching modules were applied to 12 students in the study group. While preparing for the program, the sessions were structured by adding professional coaching techniques by considering the sub-dimensions of both the career decision self-efficacy scale and the career stress scale. In the content of the sessions, homework to be given outside the sessions was planned and it was thought that these assignments would play an effective role in the career development of the students. In this study, while planning the sessions, is focused on the students' awareness of the concept of career, learning about professions, knowing themselves correctly, setting goals, making plans, and generating ideas about the solution to possible problems. In the first 60-minute session of the program, the student was acquainted in detail and the program and process were explained in general terms. Information was given about coaching. The objectives and how this process will work were discussed in detail, the rules during coaching practices were explained to the consultee by giving a contract form, and the contract was made. In the second 60-minute session of the program, the importance of self-evaluation for the right career choice was discussed by asking the student what the right self-evaluation means for the consultee and how he will understand that he/she is evaluated correctly. The interests, talents, and values of the student; their role in career choice was discussed and the student was asked to identify and list their interests, talents, and values. Finally, to enable the student to evaluate himself better, "Swot Analysis" and "Johari Window" were applied to the consultee. In the third 60-minute session of the program, it is aimed to determine the professional personality type of the consultee and which personality type the student wants to work with under the same conditions. In the fourth 60-minute session of the program, goal setting and tips for effective goal setting were discussed with the student and effective goal setting studies were carried out. At this stage, the steps to be taken by the consultee to reach the goal are planned and the concept of setting short, medium and long-term goals is discussed. In the fifth 60-minute session of the program, when the student gets his dream job, what he will do ten years later and where he sees himself are evaluated. In this process, possible solutions to the problems that the student may encounter are discussed and alternative perspectives are studied in the form of what can be done at this point. Thus, it is aimed to support the student in solving their problems. Moreover, it is discussed what students should pay attention to create a good resume (CV) and what he/she needs for successful job interviews. In the last 60-minute session of the program, a general evaluation of the sessions was made, and the student's achievements were discussed. The evaluation was made on whether the goals set in the first session were achieved by discussing with the student how the program went and the level of meeting their expectations and the current stress levels. The session was terminated by requesting a re-filling of the CDSE and KCSI. By success, we

mean changes in scale. The changes were reflected quantitatively in the results of the scales. As a result, it was seen that the coaching program we implemented increased the career decision self-efficacy of the students and reduced their career stress levels.

2.5. Statistical Analysis

Statistical analyses of the data obtained in our study were made using SPSS 23.0 data analysis program. Before starting statistical analysis, the accuracy and conformity of the data to normality were measured using the variance homogeneity test (Levene's Test). Together with this, t-test was used to determine whether there was a difference in the pre-test of the Career Decision Self-Efficacy Scale and Korean Career Stress Inventory Scale of the experimental and control groups. To search for answers to the hypotheses of the study, the data collected in accordance with the mixed research pattern (split-plot) was taken as an experimental coaching practice argument, pre-test scores as covariate final-test scores as dependent variables and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) were performed. Categorical data were summarized with 'n and %' and continuous data as mean and standard deviation. $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically meaningful in the results of the analyses.

3. Findings

A total of 24 students, including 13 females (54.2%) and 11 males (45.8%), aged between 22 and 26, participated in the study. Although the average age of all students was 23.5 ± 0.83 , there was no significant difference between the average age of males and females ($p > 0.05$). When the groups were evaluated in terms of experimental and control groups, the students in the control group were 7 females and 5 males; the students in the experimental group were found to be 6 females and 6 males. There was no significant difference between the groups when the experimental and control groups were compared in terms of age and gender ($p > 0.05$). Age and gender distributions of the cases by the group are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Age and Gender Distributions of Students in the Experimental and Control Group

Age	Experimental Group		Control Group	
	Male (n=6)	Daughter (n=6)	Male (n=5)	Daughter (n=7)
22	1 (8,3%)	-	-	-
23	2 (16,7%)	3 (25%)	3 (25%)	3 (25%)
24	3 (25%)	3 (25%)	1 (8,3%)	3 (25%)
25	-	-	-	1(8,3%)
26	-	-	1 (8,3%)	-

To evaluate the income levels of the students in the whole group in terms of socio-demographic data, it was determined that 1 (4.2%) family had an income of 1500₺ or less, 16 (66.7%) families had an income between 1500-5000₺, and 7 (29.2%) families had an income of 5000₺ or more. Compared to students in the experimental and control group in terms of income levels of families, 1 family of students in the experimental group was at a low socioeconomic level, 7 families were at a moderate socioeconomic level and 4 families were at high socioeconomic levels; It was determined that 9 families of students in the control group were at the middle socioeconomic level and 3 families were at high socioeconomic levels. In this respect, there was no significant difference between the groups ($p > .05$). Details are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Distribution of Income Levels of Students in the Entire Group

Income Level	N	%
Under 1,500	1	4,2
1500-5000	16	66,7

£5000 and above	7	29,2
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When the students in the whole group were examined in terms of their mothers' education levels, it was determined that the number of mothers who graduated from primary school was 8 (33.3%), the number of mothers with secondary school degrees was 6 (25%), the number of mothers with a high school degree was 7 (29.2%) and the number of mothers with an associate degree was 3 (12.5%). When the students were examined in terms of their father's education levels, it was determined that the number of fathers who graduated from primary school was 5 (20.8%), and the number of fathers with a secondary school degree was 7 (29.2%), the number of fathers with a high school degree was 5 (20.8%), the number of fathers with an associate degree was 6 (25%) and the number of fathers with a bachelor's degree was 1 (4.2%). There was no statistically significant difference in the levels of maternal and paternal education ($p > .05$). Parental education levels are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Parental Education Levels of Students in The Entire Group

Training Levels	Mother		Father	
	n	%	N	%
Primary school	8	33,3	5	20,8
Secondary school	6	25	7	29,2
High school	7	29,2	5	20,8
Associate	3	12,5	6	25
Bachelor	-		1	4,2

When the whole group was examined in terms of mother occupations, it was determined that the number of mothers who were housewives was 17 (70.8%), the number of mothers who retired was 3 (12.5%), the number of mothers working in the private sector was 3 (12.5%), and the number of mothers working as civil servants was 1 (4.2%). When the whole group was examined in terms of paternal occupational groups, it was determined that 11 (45.8%) fathers were self-employed, 7 (29.2%) fathers were retired, 4 (16.7%) fathers worked as civil servants, 1 (4.2%) father was a bank employee, and 1 (4.2%) father was a farmer.

Levene's Test was conducted to assess whether the students in the experimental and control group represented the same population, and according to this test, the variants were homogenous in terms of both career decision efficacy expectation ($p = .787$, $p > .05$), career stress ($p = .294$; $p > .05$).

Coefficients of skewness were examined to observe whether the scores of the experimental and control groups from the Career Decision Self-Efficacy Scale and Korean Career Stress Inventory Scale had normal distribution (Table 4).

According to this, CDSE=.35 and Career Stress=-.49 were obtained for the experimental group and CDSE= -.25 and Career Stress=. -03 were obtained for the control group. When the relevant literature is examined, the fact that these values are not greater than +1.0 and less than -1.0 is an important indicator of normal distribution (Leech, Barrett and Morgan, 2005). In other words, it was observed that the scores of the scales were distributed normally.

Table 4: Skewness Values of Experimental and Control Groups

	Experimental group	Control group
CDSE*	.35	-.25
Career Stress	.49	-.03

*CDSE: Career Decision Self-Efficacy Expectation

It was questioned whether the values obtained from the Career Decision Self-Efficacy Expectation Scale and Career Stress Scale of the experimental and control groups met the basic assumptions of parametric tests and for this purpose, the scores of the experimental and control groups from the preliminary tests of career decision self-efficacy expectation and career stress scales were compared by t-test. When the findings are evaluated, it is seen that there is no significant difference in career stress between the experimental and control groups ($p=.114$; $p>.05$), but there is a significant difference between both groups in terms of career decision self-efficacy expectation ($p=.02$; $p<.05$). Accordingly, when the averages of the groups are examined, it is seen that the students who make up the control group feel more competent in their career decisions than the students of the experimental group.

T-test was used for independent samples to determine whether the scores of all students from the career decision self-efficacy expectation pre-test by gender differed and it was determined that there was no significant difference between the groups in terms of career decision self-efficacy of male and female students ($t= 0.584$, $p>0.05$). In the same way, t-test was used for independent samples to determine whether the scores of all students from the career stress pretest by gender differed and it was determined that there was no significant difference between the groups in terms of career stress of male and female students ($t= 0.182$, $p>0.05$). T-test was used for independent samples to determine whether the scores of all students differed from their final test of career decision self-efficacy by gender, and it was determined that there was no significant difference between the groups in terms of the final test of career decision self-efficacy expectation of male and female students ($t=-0.542$, $p>0.05$). In the same way, t-test was used for independent samples to determine whether the scores of all students from the career stress final test by gender differed and it was determined that there was no significant difference between the groups in terms of the final test of career stress of male and female students ($t=-0.556$, $p>0.05$).

3.1.Findings on the Career Decision Self-Efficacy Expectation Scale

It was examined whether the total scores of the experimental and control groups from the Career Decision Self-Efficacy Expectation Scale changed after the

career coaching process with the students in the experimental group and the results were shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Average and Standard Deviations of

		Experimental (n=12)		Group Control Group (n=12)	
		\bar{x}	<i>S</i>	\bar{x}	<i>S</i>
CDSSES*	Pre-Test	78	13,8	93	15,3
	Final Test	112	8,5	97	16,5

*CDSSES: Pre-test and Final-test Scores of Experimental and Control Groups

When Table 5 was examined, it was determined that the final score increased to 112 points after the career coaching experimental procedure while the average pre-test score of the experimental group from the Career Decision Self-Efficacy Expectation Scale was 78 points. The control group's CDSSES score average was 93 in the preliminary test; 97 points in the final test. In order to determine whether the difference between the average of the pre-test and final-test scores received by the students in the experimental and control group from the CDSSES was significant, in other words, whether the career coaching process applied to the students in the experimental group had a positive effect on the students, a unidirectional covariance test was applied and as a result of the covariance analysis, the mean of the CDSSES score was found to be 116.62 (± 3.12) for the experimental group and 92.62 (± 3.12) for the control group. ANCOVA analysis results were evaluated to test whether the difference between averages was significant, and the findings were given in Table 6.

Table 6: Covariance Analysis (ANCOVA) Results on CDSSES Pre-test – Final-test Scores of Experimental and Control Groups

Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	of SD	Squares Average	F	P*	Partial Eta Squared (PES)
CDSSES Pre-Test	1650,87	1	1650,87	16,17	,001	,435
Group	2681,05	1	2681,05	26,26	,000	,556
Error	2143,71	21	102,08			
Sum	267873	24				

*p<0.05

When table 6 was examined, when the CDSSES pre-test scores were controlled as the covariate, the experimental practice (career coaching) was instrumental in increasing students' career decision self-efficacy expectations [$F_{(1-21)}=26.26$; $p=.000<.005$]. When you look at the PES value of the same row, it is

seen that there is an impact magnitude of 55%. From this point on, it can be said that the career coaching program applied to university students positively affects the level of career decision self-efficacy expectation of its students by 55%.

3.2. Findings on the Career Stress Scale

The total scores of the experimental and control groups from the Career Stress Scale were examined and the results were shown in Table 7.

Table 7: Average and Standard Deviations of CSS Pre-test and Final-test Scores of Experimental and Control Groups

		Experimental Group		Control Group	
		\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S
CAREER	Pre-Test	61,08	3,25	51,53	4,76
STRESS	Final-Test	26,91	1,61	44,33	6,08

When table 7 was examined, it was determined that the final score decreased to 26.91 after the career coaching experimental procedure, while the average pre-test score of the experimental group from the Career Stress Scale was 61.08 points. The control group's CSS score average was 51.53 in the preliminary test; 44.33 points in the final test. In order to determine whether the difference between the average of the pretest and final test scores of the students in the experimental and control group from the Career Stress Scale was meaningful, in other words, the career coaching process applied to the students in the experimental group had a positive effect on the students a unidirectional covariance test was applied and as a result of covariance analysis, the mean score of CSS was found to be 25.068 (± 4.38) for the experimental group and 46.18 (± 4.38) for the control group. The results of the Ancova analysis were evaluated to test whether the difference between averages was significant and the findings were given in Table 8.

Table 8: Covariance Analysis (ANCOVA) Results of Experimental and Control Groups on CSS Pre-Test – Final-Test Scores

Variance Source		Sum of Squares	SD	Squares Average	F	P*	Partial Eta Squared (PES)
Career Pretest	Stress	665,78	1	665,78	3,06	,095	,127
Group		2381,41	1	2381,41	10,95	,003	,343
Error		4565,8	21	217,41			
Sum		37511	24				

*p|<0.05

When table 8 was examined, when the CSS pre-examination scores were controlled as the covariate, the experimental practice (career coaching) was

effective in reducing the career stress of students [$F_{(1-21)}=10.95$; $p=.003<.005$]. Looking at the PES value of the same row, it is seen that there is an impact magnitude of 34%. From this point on, it can be said that the career coaching program applied to university students positively affects the level of career stress of the students reducing it by 34%.

4. Discussion

In this research, it is aimed to examine the impact of career coaching practices on career decision self-efficacy and career stress levels of university students. The mean age of the students who participated in the study was 23.5 ± 0.83 , and there was no significant difference between the groups when evaluated in terms of gender and socio-demographic data. When examined whether the career decisions of all students differed in terms of gender, there was no significant difference between the groups in our study. Although there are similar studies in the literature to our study (Concannon & Barrow, 2012; Coon, 2009; Nawaz & Gilani, 2011; Özyürek, 2001); contrary to our findings, there are also studies that show significant differences in gender (Dogan, Özgün, Demir & Türkmen 2016: 794; Wolfe & Betz, 2004; Gianakos, 2001). When the studies with gender differences were examined, it was determined that while women traditionally tended towards the field of careers in which they could express themselves, men felt more competent in the fields of science and technology and turned to careers in that field (Bandura, 1997; Bandura, 2006). When we examine similar research to this study, we can explain that there is no difference in terms of gender as gender roles may be a more important factor than gender in career decision-making self-efficacy. In this respect, individuals are influenced by the sense that they place their thoughts on being male or female in which field they will successfully pursue their careers (Bandura, 2006; Abdalla, 1995; Nawaz & Gilani, 2011).

In our country, the effects of different variables on careers were examined in career studies. When the literature was examined, it was seen that students with high career decision-making self-efficacy levels were able to make the right career choice for themselves and successfully complete their developmental periods in terms of profession (Ziebell, 2010; Rogers & Creed, 2011). Research conducted by Ziebell (2010) on university students found that university students with high levels of career decision-making had low career indecisiveness levels and high levels of career maturity. In addition, the number of studies examining the impact of coaching on careers is very limited. In this respect, this study is the first in our country within the scope of career coaching practices for university students.

One of the first hypotheses of our research, career decision self-efficacy, was looked at before and after the coaching practice and the score averages of the students in the experimental group who were intervened by applying career coaching were found to be significantly higher than the scores of the students in the control group who did not practice career coaching on the Career Decision Self-Efficacy Expectation scale. This means that the practice of career coaching is effective in increasing students' career decision self-efficacy expectations. When the literature was examined, it was seen that experimental studies applied to

university students abroad had positive effects on career decision self-efficacy. For example, in the study conducted by Maples and Luzzo (2005), it was determined that the career decision-making self-efficacy scores of university students who were given career psychological counseling were significantly higher than those who did not. In the study conducted by Nguyen (2005), which measured the effect of career group interventions on career decision-making self-efficacy and problem-solving levels, it was determined that group counseling intervention and problem-solving training increased the level of career decision-making self-efficacy of university students. Reese and Miller (2006) prepared a 15-week program to examine the impact of the career development course on the level of career decision-making self-efficacy of university students in their work with students who do not have any career preferences and applied it to students. According to the results of the research, it was concluded that the university students who took the course had an increase in their self-efficacy levels in making career decisions in general compared to those who did not. Similarly, Scott and Ciani (2008) conducted studies to measure the impact of the career research program on the self-efficacy and professional identities of students in making career decisions, and as a result of this study, they determined that the career research program was effective in increasing the level of self-efficacy of university students in making career decisions. Furthermore, a study to measure the impact of psycho-educational programs on the career decision self-efficacy of university students found that participants' level of self-efficacy in making career decisions increased (Essing & Kelly, 2013). When the studies in our country, which are like this study, are examined, there are a few studies examining the effect of coaching on career. However, it is seen that those studies are focused more on group studies rather than effects on individuals. In this respect, when the literature was examined, a study with similar findings was conducted by Işık (2010) as a group study. In this study, it was concluded that the students' career decision self-efficacy expectation levels increased significantly after a 10-session career intervention based on social cognitive career theory given to university students. This study which is expressed in the successful practices in the literature while the career coaching program was being prepared, is thought to improve the level of personal self-efficacy expectation (Bandura, 1977, 1982, 1995, 1997; Lent et al., 1994) forming the basis of the concept of career decision-making self-efficacy with four key informative resources, which was also formed by taking into account the five self-efficacy areas that were put forward for career choice by Crites (1961, 1981) and formed the basis of the concept of career decision-making self-efficacy.

The second hypothesis of the study is whether the level of career stress changed before and after the coaching practice, and it was determined that the Career Stress scale score averages of the students in the experimental group who were intervened by applying career coaching were significantly lower than the scores of the students in the control group who did not practice career coaching. As a result of this study, it can be said that the career coaching program applied to university students positively affects the level of career stress of the students reducing it by 34%. This means that the practice of career coaching is effective in reducing students' career stress levels. When the literature is examined, there is no study that directly examines the effect of coaching practice on career stress in our country. In a study conducted by Yavuzarslan et al. (2016) in our country, it was

examined what are the factors that constitute the career stress of 5.6 million university students using TURKSTAT (Turkish Statistical Institute) data and because of the study, it was determined that programs and courses for students can be effective in reducing and preventing stress. In this respect, individual coaching practices can be very useful in reducing students' stress levels and neutralizing their roots of anxiety. Studies carried out in our country and abroad are mostly aimed at determining the factors and dimensions that constitute career stress and examining the relationship of these factors with each other. In studies, it was found that the factors that constitute career stress were internal and environmentally related (Kaplanoglu, 2014), and stress symptoms were determined physically, behaviourally, and psychologically (Durna, 2006). When we examined whether the career stress of all students differed in terms of gender, there was no significant difference between the groups in our study. When the literature is examined, there are findings in similar (Durna, 2006) and different (Grapes and arc., 2018; Sky, 2009; Strong, 2001) directions to our study in terms of gender. In this context, it is thought that studies with a wider sampling are needed.

5. Conclusions And Recommendations

In our study, both quantitative and qualitative research methods were used to examine the effect of career coaching practices on career decision self-efficacy and career stress levels of university students. A total of 24 people, 12 (6 females and 6 males) for the experimental group and 12 (7 females and 5 males) for the control group, were included in the study. In this study, which was conducted by using the convenience sampling method, senior students were informed about the research and socio-demographic form, career decision self-efficacy scale and career stress scale were applied. In the study, the independent variable was coaching practices, the dependent variable was determined as career decision self-efficacy and career stress, and a mixed design was used with the control group who applied a pre-test and final-test.

This study is a pioneering study conducted within the scope of career coaching practices for university students in our country. In our study, it was determined that the career coaching program applied to university senior students increased the level of expectation of career decision self-efficacy by 55% and reduced the level of career stress by 34%. As a result, career coaching application increases the career decision self-efficacy of the students and reduces the level of career stress. In the light of this knowledge, which also supports the literature, with the increase in career coaching practices in universities, future generations can be enabled to become more competent and successful individuals in their careers and experience less career stress. With the implementation of both individual applications and group studies, support can be provided to reduce students' anxiety and stress while increasing their self-efficacy for their careers. Individual coaching sessions can help students reduce their stress and anxiety or support them in neutralizing their anxiety-causing roots. Especially if such practices are started from the first days of the university, the psychological factors that may occur can be prevented before they occur. In this respect, coaching practices can become

preventive intervention programs. The fact that studies outside Turkey with similar results to this study were generally conducted in the form of group studies shows that there is a need for individual studies in the future. In this respect, quantitative and qualitative studies where individual coaching is applied should be supported.

In future studies, the effect of coaching practices on other factors such as students' career maturity and career tendencies can also be investigated. In addition, apart from the Presidential Human Resources Office Career Centres, which have just started in higher education in our country, the career centres in some universities have recently begun to increase their activities and are trying to establish the system. Moreover, in some institutions and organizations or workplaces, there are individuals who mentor students and interns who are new to the field and help them as a coach. It is foreseen that in the future, the activities of career centres will increase, and they will act with a common theme and coaches will provide more services in the fields of vocational guidance.

One of the limitations of the study was the fact that the research was carried out in a single centre and the number of samples was low. In future studies, multi-centre research and increasing the number of samples can be carried out. Because the study is the first in Turkey, it is thought that the results of the study will shed light on the literature and contribute scientifically.

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